

A NOVEL PROPOSED FUSION METHOD

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Abstract: In this paper, two proposed fusion methods will be proposed for merging important information from more than one source for the purpose of either making final image with high quality compared to the input images or making final image holding more information that captured in the input images depending on some important extracted features from the input images. The first method merge images depending on edges information in each pixel by applying one order prewitt method for edge detection then calculating the ratio related to each image for this position then calculating new pixel value for this place in the output image, while the second proposed method working by estimating texture unit number value in each pixel in the input images and merging pixels by applying proposed techniques for the purpose of calculating output pixel which reflect good degree of the proposed feature with accepted compatible degree with neighbouring eight pixels. The results of the proposed methods checked with some suitable metrics for measuring the quality of the output images compared with the standard methods like maximum, minimum, ratio, wavelet,... and the result of the proposed method reflect good and perfect quality for the output images and this result can be expected because fusion operation performed according to effected visible features that making fused images with good quality.

Keywords: Texture number, Fusion, Edge, Mutual information, prewitt masks

I. INTRODUCTION

Image fusion:can be clarified as an operation of merging pixels information from more than one source for the purpose of producing image with more information compared to initial state of the input images if the initial images for different scenes or producing enhanced copy against to all raw images if the raw images for same scene in different states of pixels features[1]. Generally there are four levels or kinds in image fusion as illustrate in fig. (1).

Fig. 1 Image fusion kinds

A. Pixel-Fusion

This kind of fusion techniques directly deal with value of the gray level of pixels or colour degree so the output images from these algorithms are fine and more compatible in pixel visibility for the dedicated position, the important algorithms in this level work by focusing on all important and desired information extracted from specific parts of the raw images [2]. These fusion state divided into (three) kinds:

- 1) Linear techniques like the operation of taking average among pixels gray level or may be among coefficient of suitable transform like PCA by deciding suitable ratio for each position [3].
- 2) Non-linear methods: such as taking pixels with minimum value or pixels with maximum gray level number among all raw numbers in each position.
- 3) MR (multi-resolution) techniques: these techniques divided into two groups:
 - Pyramid group: raw images in this group decomposed and then construct a pyramid of edges with various resolutions then combining information of this pyramid in suitable way [3].
 - DWT (Discrete-wavelet-transform) groups: these groups of fusion techniques performed among the coefficients in parts LL, LH, HL and HH regions [4] that produced after applying one of the wavelet families transforms as shown in Fig. (2).

a-Img.(1)

b-Img.(2)

c- output img.

Fig. 2 wavelet group of fusion

B. Feature-Fusion:

Extracting suitable and desired properties from the raw images at the beginning then merging these features by adopting suitable techniques [5].

C. Region – Fusion

The main idea in this kind of fusion methods is performing suitable segmentation method to divide raw images into number of regions (or dividing into blocks) then perform proposed method for merging segments or blocks for the purpose of producing accepted output fused image [1].

D. Decision-fusion

In this kind of fusion methods the algorithm combines information from different sensors by applying Boolean operation (AND, OR) or taking suitable ratio from each sensor in order to discover better decision for various sensors [3].

The most important goals for fusion operation are

- 1) Enhance signal to noise ratio by reducing noise [4].
- 2) Enhance image resolution (special).
- 3) Construct images that may be more information or better clearing compared to all raw images [5].

The general usefulness of fusion operation is to detect and discover the wanted information from the raw images as a first step and then combining them into suitable and decided way in order to generate results with better features that required for many algorithms and for producing more suitable image that used in the followed processes for making results more accurate, these accurate information provide better credibility to the observer or computer [6] with better resistance to the difficult conditions [3] and assist in supporting three recognition operations for specific object that are detect, recognize and identify.

Many applications now depend on taking results from fusion techniques such as defect inspection, remote sensing, military monitoring and medical diagnosis [6]. The most important kinds of fusion methods from structure side are:

- 1) Hierarchical as shown in fig.(3a),
- 2) Overall as shown in fig.(3b), and
- 3) Arbitrary As shown in Fig. (3c).

Fusion techniques sometimes need applying some preprocessing operation for the raw images for the purpose of making raw images owning either conformable representation or compatible representation [7]. Monitoring systems is one of the most important systems that used fusion techniques because the difficulty in monitoring many science increased greatly with growing the number of monitoring sciences simultaneously [8] as well as required information constructed in perfect pattern, with better time and accepted cost [7]. The fusion techniques raise the final certainty of the system and help in supporting the total accuracy of the system [8] also help in supporting accuracy in some cases like the total failure of some sensors or errors occurring [9].

Fig. 3 Fusion structures

II. RELATED WORK

- 1) Tawfiq A. Al-Asadi in [2], Suggest a new algorithm for running fusion operation among many input images for the purpose of finding only two output images that have important information from all input matrices and this operation can be performed in two ways the first one depend on dividing matrix into blocks with taking the maximum value for the first position and calculating variance between centre and eight neighbouring pixel for all matrices then taking the pixel that produce minimum variance and so on until producing the first output image while the second way start by taking minimum value for the first position and progressing step by step for adding pixel after pixel that produce maximum variance with the eight neighbouring pixels.
- 2) Song Liu, et. al., in [11], Introduce a novel method for producing new texture image from perfect high resolution image that produced by using (HD RGB) camera, then perform some operations for making the number of pixels in the texture image greater than voxels in the 3-D constructed object and reducing the final number of suggested polygon by eliminating unwanted positions and ignoring them then in the last step performing operation of mapping constructed texture to the decided polygon as the designer suggest.
- 3) Wencheng Wang et.al. in [12] Suggest an algorithm for solving some problem that related to multi –focus problem by performing fusion operation that depend essentially on Laplacian pyramid by taking large number of images for the wanted scene and decomposed them as the first step of the proposed system then performing suggested fusion operation between levels of Laplacian pyramid then as a last step performing inverse Laplacian operation for the purpose of producing high quality fused image. As shown in the search, the results considered as accepted with good quality compared to the other algorithms.
- 4) Paul Hill, et.al. in [13], suggest a perfect fusion algorithm for producing single perfect image by performing two series of isolated operations one line of operation consist of performing importance value for each coefficient that produced by applying complex wavelet transform and the second line of operation consist of performing filtering operation for the purpose of improving contrast and brightness for pixels of given image and this line for preparing image and make the followed operation produced good and perfect results. The proposed system produced accepted results that can be considered as quantities and perfect compared to the other techniques.
- 5) Tawfiq A. Al-Asadi In [1], suggest a novel method for performing multi resolution method by applying Haar wavelet transform (with high and low filters) for all input images then perform fusion technique among wavelet coefficients in order to produce one fused image that represent the effect of more than one light source on specific object in order to simulate the specific object as 3-D object.

III. THE PROPOSED SYSTEM

The suggested techniques can be produced by the following steps for each method of them as follow

A. First method depending on edges features

The novel method for merging images depending on edges features which can be explained by the Bloch diagram in figure (4) and as shown this method consist of many steps in order to discover the last fused image as follows

- 1- Performing suitable mask for calculating edges values in each position of the input matrices for the input images by applying horizontal and vertical prewitt masks as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
 H_{Prewitt} &= \begin{bmatrix} -1 & -1 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \\
 V_{Prewitt} &= \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}
 \end{aligned}
 \dots (1)$$

Then after applying the above filters for each pixel in the input images the following image will be founded that hold edges information for all pixels as follows

$$Edge_{horizontal}(x,y) = -n(x-1,y-1) - n(x-1,y) - n(x-1,y+1) + n(x+1,y-1) + n(x+1,y) + n(x+1,y+1) \dots (2)$$

$$Edge_{vertical}(x,y) = -n(x-1,y-1) - n(x,y-1) - n(x+1,y-1) + n(x-1,y+1) + n(x,y+1) + n(x+1,y+1) \dots (3)$$

$$Edge_{final}(x,y) = \sqrt{Edge_{horizontal}(x,y)^2 + Edge_{vertical}(x,y)^2} \dots (4)$$

The results of applying above equations for Prewitt edge detection (PED) can be explained in Fig.(5)

Fig. (4) block diagram for method (1)

Fig. 5 Prewitt method for edges detection

Prewitt masks will be applied for each pixel in the input images for in order to estimate the ratio that will be used in calculating the contribution of each image in the final value of the pixel in output fused image.

2- Estimating the ratio that will be used in constructing fused image:- after applying Prewitt edges masks in every position of the input matrices, the contribution of each image in the decided position will be discovered by dividing final edges values in specific image by the summing of the edges values for that position in all input images as follow

$$TEV(x,y) = FEV1(x,y) + FEV2(x,y) + \dots + FEVn(x,y) \dots (5)$$

Where

TEV(x, y) is the total edge strength in position (x,y)

FEV1^(x,y) is the value of the edge in image (1) in position (x,y) and so on for other raw images

$$\begin{aligned} FFR1(x,y) &= \frac{FEV1(x,y)}{TEV(x,y)}, \\ FFR2(x,y) &= \frac{FEV2(x,y)}{TEV(x,y)}, \\ FFRn(x,y) &= \frac{FEVn(x,y)}{TEV(x,y)}, \end{aligned} \quad \dots(6)$$

Where

FFR1 is final fusion ratio for image (1) and the same state for other raw images.

The last step in the edge fusion method is smoothing final fusion ratio for all images in order to produce fine and accept changes in the final color of the fused among all image pixels and its neighboring pixels by applying mean filter, and finally estimating final value in each position by multiplying the ratio of fusion for each raw image by the gray level of the pixel in dedicate position as follow

$$FPV(x,y) = FFR1(x,y) * IP1(x,y) + FFR2(x,y) * IP2(x,y) + \dots + FFRn(x,y) * IPn(x,y) \quad \dots (7)$$

Where

FPV(x, y) is the final pixel value in the position (x, y).

IP1(x, y) is the pixel value of image 1 in position (x, y)

After performing the above equations the final fused image will be constructed as shown in Fig. (6)

Fig. 6 Edge fusion method

B. Second method depending on Texture feature

The second technique of the proposed system can be named as texture fusion method and this fusion method can be explained as shown in Fig. (7). The first step is to estimate texture number for each pixel of the input image performed by applying equation (12) for each position in the input matrices and calculate texture number as a relation with the eight neighboring pixels around specific position as follows

$$TE_x = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{when } pv_x < pv_o \\ 1 & \text{when } pv_x = pv_o \\ 2 & \text{when } pv_x > pv_o \dots \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Fig. 7 Block diagram of method (2) of the proposed system

Where

TE_x represent texture unit element in position (x)

PV_x represent pixel value in position (x)

PV_0 represent pixel value in center position as shown in Fig. 8

V_2	V_3	V_4
V_1	V_0	V_5
V_8	V_7	V_6

Fig. 8 eight neighbouring pixels around specific position

$$TEXU_n = 3^{x-1} TE_x \quad x = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 8 \quad \dots (9)$$

Where

$TEXU_n$ is texture unit number for specific position in the matrix.

The number of Texture unit consider as local feature in the specific position so this value represent an important index of the pixel for estimating each ratio for all pixels that will be helped in constructing final fused image as explained in Fig. (9).

Fig. 9 texture image

- 1- finding the ratio for each position in raw images for constructing final fused image with accepted good value of texture as follows

$$SoTU = TEXU_1 + TEXU_2 + \dots + TEXU_n \quad \dots (10)$$

$$TRI_1 = \frac{TEXU_1}{SoTU}, TRI_2 = \frac{TEXU_2}{SoTU}, \dots, TRI_n = \frac{TEXU_n}{SoTU} \dots (11)$$

Where

SoTU is summation of texture units

TRI_1 is the texture ratio for image (1) and so on for other images

In texture fusion method the texture ratio value also will not be fixed for reflecting textures of all positions without alleviation of wanted features of texture in that position.

- 2- building final fused image by summing multiplication of all pixels values for input images in the specific position by the discovered ratios for each position in all input images as follows

$$FPV(l, f) = TRI_1(l, f) * IP_1(l, f) + TRI_2(l, f) * IP_2(l, f) + \dots + TRI_n(l, f) * IP_n(l, f) \dots (12)$$

Where $FPV(x, y)$ is final value in position (x, y)

Fig. (10) Explained the steps of applying previous equations

Fig. 10 Texture fusion

IV. RESULTS

Fig. 11 Edge fusion for similar images with different blurring regions

When the proposed techniques will be applied on different images the following states are found as follow Case (1):
First fusion method with same images which have different damaged regions as explained in Fig. (11)

Case (2) First method with Different sciences as shown in Fig. (12)

Fig. 12 Edge fusion for Different images

Case(3): Second method with same science which have different damaged regions as shown in Fig. (13)

Fig. (13) Texture fusion for similar images with different blurring regions
Case (4) Second fusion method with Different images as shown in Fig. (14)

Fig. 14 Texture fusion for different images

There are some metrics for improving the degree of perfect fusion methods, important metrics can introduced as follow , Peak Signal Noise Ratio (PSNR): PSNR between pure images and final image will be estimated and large number means perfect results in evaluation.

$$PSNR = 10 \log_{10} \frac{(L-1)^2}{\sum_{m=1}^w \sum_{n=1}^h [z(m,n) - o(m,n)]^2} \quad \dots (13)$$

Where : L is the number of gray levels

Z is the input matrix (image) , O is the output image , w and h are image dimensions

- 1- Mutual information (MI): The final fused image will be Tested with each input image without considering the place of specific color and large number means good results in evaluation.

$$MI_{AB}(a, b) = \sum_{a,b} P_{AB}(a, b) \log \frac{P_{AB}(a, b)}{P_A(a)P_B(b)} \quad \dots (14)$$

Where ; $P_A(a)$ is the probability of gray level (A)

$P_{AB}(a, b)$ is the joint probability of gray levels (A) and (B)

- 2- Edge information (EI) metric decide if irregular effect will be happened due to fusion operation and large number means un accepting results in evaluation.

$$Q^{AF}(m, n) = Q_g^{AF}(m, n) Q_e^{AF}(m, n) \quad \dots (15)$$

Where

$Q_g^{AF}(m, n)$ is the amount of edge values in a pixel with location (m, n) in image (A) appear in final image.

$Q_e^{AF}(m, n)$ is the amount orientation values in a pixel with location (m, n) in image (A) appear in the fused image.

Table(1) results of quality metrics

	State	PSNR	MI	EI
Case (1)	Edge fusion	18.2	30.720	0.920
	Mean fusion	18.0	27.160	0.922
Case (2)	Edge fusion	18.6	15.270	0.640
	Mean fusion	17.2	13.190	0.640
Case (3)	Texture fusion	16.4	29.150	0.990
	Mean fusion	15.8	28.840	0.992
Case (4)	Texture fusion	13.8	13.860	0.740
	Mean fusion	13.8	13.350	0.740

V. CONCLUSION

There is no one claimed that when the raw images are similar then the final fused image must be similar as well in all techniques of fusion because fusion operation focuses naturally on some features of the input image in order to transform to the fused image with ignoring other unwanted information as well as if information from two different patches become similar these states don't reflect perfect or good method because the position is an important case that must be taken in account for comparing two images, so these metrics may be considered as unreliable metrics but fusion method must have some adaptive mechanism rather than considering fixed mechanism for all positions in the image and performing fixed state to all cases while there are some pixels have with much great important than other ones depending on some specific features in this pixel. The traditional methods for performing fusion operation are not accepted because mean operation hides some important regions by taking half ratio of it and half ratio from another picture either if it without important information, Selected ratio also not accepted because the selected ratio must be related to some important features that differ depending on the type of image or the place in that image, Selecting maximum/minimum pixel, as well as produce, degrade image with huge and un uniformed changes among neighboring pixels. The suggested methods estimate the final fused image by taking in account some specific and important features to decide the last state for each pixel in input images depending on the availability of these features in that image, the exploit features in the proposed techniques are edge value and texture number and as I thought (with explained proven) these features produce very good and perfect results as shown in this search.

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